

Estimating the effect of punching on out-of-plane bending fatigue of steel sheet specimens

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ABSTRACT

Sheet metal punching is an important process in manufacturing of heavy-duty vehicle chassis components. The cut edges have a detrimental effect on high cycle fatigue life in uniaxial- and in-plane-bending but the reduction is less pronounced in out-of-plane bending. This paper aims to explain the reduced process sensitivity in out-of-plane bending fatigue, to quantify the high cycle fatigue life reduction at different load ratios, and to propose a methodology for fatigue life estimation. This could enhance the possibilities to identify critical load cases of chassis components, to judge whether fatigue life improving post-processes are necessary, and to locate critical initiation sites for fatigue. Fatigue testing of punched and polished specimens was conducted, and the punching process and four-point bending were simulated using FEM. The results were used to estimate crack initiation site, fatigue life reduction, and for validating the predictions. Fatigue life reduction is found to increase with increased load ratio, but to a smaller extent than expected. A contributing factor the reduced tensile residual stresses due to plasticity during the first load cycle. The reduced process sensitivity as compared to uniaxial fatigue could be explained by the separate locations of crack initiation and high tensile residual stresses in the cut edge. Specimen orientation seems to have a minor influence on the fatigue life. Only improving the outer surfaces, and not the central parts of the cut edge, could increase the high cycle fatigue life for pulsating and reversed loading.

1. Introduction

Truck chassis components and wheels often features a significant amount of holes [1,2]. Mechanical punching is commonly used to produce these holes due to the low production times and costs associated with the method [3]. One of the main concerns using punching is the possible detrimental effect on High Cycle Fatigue (HCF) life of the components [1,4], which is critical due to the fluctuating loads acting on the chassis and wheels during service [4,5]. Extensive studies on how punching affect the uniaxial fatigue life of steel specimens have been presented over the years. Increased understanding of the manufacturing process effect on fatigue life is hoped to enable reducing safety factors in design and hence achieving weight reductions. In [6] uniaxial fatigue testing of thick grade 700–960 MPa steel specimens with a punched hole was conducted. It was shown that a small cutting clearance could

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improve fatigue life. In [1] it was shown that two-stage punching could improve uniaxial fatigue life of thick S500MC specimens, as compared to one-stage punching. The effect of shear cutting on uniaxial fatigue of press hardened steel specimens was examined in [7]. Other notable studies on the effect of shear cutting on uniaxial fatigue are presented in [8–10] where it for example is shown that initiation often occur in the fracture zone of the cut edge, tensile residual stresses are found in that zone, lower strength steels are less sensitive to cutting, and that fatigue life reduction from cutting is more pronounced under constant amplitude loading than under variable ditto.

Another important load case for Heavy-Duty Vehicle (HDV) chassis components and wheels is out-of-plane bending fatigue [2, 11]. Concerning this type of loading the literature is sparser. However, the effect of residual stresses on reversed loading HCF of high strength steel specimens was quantified in [12]. It was shown that for moderate cutting clearances the crack initiated in the rollover zone for the lower grade material and close to the burr for the higher grade. In [13] out-of-plane bending fatigue of high strength steel specimens featuring cut edges from milling, laser and water jet were examined. It was found that for higher stress amplitudes, with number of cycles below approximately 10^5 , the difference in fatigue performance between the cut edge conditions was minimal.

Methods to estimate fatigue reduction due to shear cutting processes have also been presented. In [12] the stabilized residual stress was used with a Goodman relationship to estimate the fatigue limit reduction. In [14] surface roughness and tensile residual stresses in the fracture zone of the cut edge were used to estimate HCF life of high strength steel and aluminum specimens.

In both methods presented above the initiation site must be known or assumed a priori. This requirement is more easily fulfilled for in-plane and uniaxial fatigue loading where the applied stress over the thickness is evenly distributed. Hence the area featuring the most critical surface condition (high surface roughness and tensile residual stresses) could also be assumed to be the fatigue crack initiation site. For punched specimens this area is usually located close to the center of the sheet thickness or close the burnish/fracture zone transition [3,15,16]. The studied load ratios in the mentioned studies [12,14] were limited, either to load ratio $R = -1$, or to $R = -1$ and $R = 0.1$.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the interaction between out-of-plane loading and the cut edge conditions from punching is not yet fully understood, and convenient methods for quantification of the fatigue life reduction is lacking. Out-of-plane fatigue of punched specimens adds complexity due to the non-uniform stress distribution through the sheet thickness with the lowest stress magnitude from the external loading appearing in the center of the thickness where the tensile residual stresses from punching are the highest and where the surface roughness could be high. The interaction between external out-of-plane loading, different load ratios, residual stresses and stress relaxation might lead to a transition in initiation site depending on the load amplitude. Hence quantifying methods relying on a known surface state where the crack initiate cannot be directly utilized.

In this work, the aim is to provide increased understanding of the effect of punching on out-of-plane bending fatigue of steel specimens for a wide range of load ratios, and an approach for estimation of the reduced high cycle fatigue life as compared to base material specimens.

To achieve this, simulations and fatigue tests were performed. The residual stress profile of the cut edge was obtained from a punching FEM-simulation according to the approach in [17], where uniaxial tensile testing is used to calibrate a plastic flow material model, and punching experiments is used to calibrate a failure model. The elastic stress concentration variation was found through a four-point bending simulation. The base material $S-N$ curve and validation experiments are obtained by bending fatigue testing of polished and punched specimens. Finally a process to estimate the most critical point for fatigue crack initiation, enabling the use of a modified version of the previously presented fatigue life estimation procedure [14], is presented.

2. Theory

2.1. Effect of punching on metal fatigue

Cutting clearance is an important punching process parameter. It is defined as the ratio of the gap between the punch and the die to the sheet thickness, see Fig. 1(a). The cut edge resulting from punching features a characteristic shape with different zones that could be described by Fig. 1(b) [17,18]. Usually the formation of burr can be avoided if a reasonable cutting clearance is used, see for example [7,17,19]. Assuming moderate clearances means that it is possible to avoid an additional geometric stress concentration that would increase the complexity of the problem.

The punching process can induce tensile residual stresses in the loading direction, which are known to have a detrimental effect on fatigue life [20]. These stresses are usually found in the rollover zone and in the fracture zone while the burnish zone and the horizontal surface next to the burr in Fig. 1(b) could feature beneficial compressive stresses [12,14,21]. The compressive residual stresses can increase both the number of cycles required to initiate and to propagate a crack a certain distance [20]. Tensile residual stresses can be treated as positive mean stress in the HCF regime [22], and positive mean stresses increase fatigue damage accumulation rate and decrease crack initiation life [23].

Decreasing the surface roughness often increases HCF life. The surface roughness at the rollover zone and the surface next to the burr is not in contact with the punch during shear cutting and could hence be assumed to remain unaffected by the process. The burnish and the fracture zone, on the other hand, are surfaces that form during the process. Usually the burnish zone has significantly lower roughness than the fracture zone [10,14].

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic illustration of punching process and cutting clearance; (b) Cut edge zones after punching. From [17], used under Creative Commons CC-BY license.

2.2. Fatigue assessment considering mean stresses

It is evident that mean stresses, resulting both from loading conditions and from process induced residual stress, must be accounted for [20,23]. This can be done in several ways. Two of the most classical empirical models to handle mean stresses are proposed by Gerber [24] and Goodman [25]. These convenient methods form the foundation for the mean stress correction used in this work, see Eqs. (5) and (19). For a more advanced probabilistic assessment of the mean stress effect Barbosa et al. [23] proposed a method to create constant life diagrams of metallic materials using an artificial neural network algorithm. This method could describe the stochastic behavior of the fatigue experiments using relatively small experimental effort.

2.3. HCF life estimation of punched specimens subject to uniaxial loading

This section summarizes the approach presented in detail in [14]. For punched specimens with known fatigue crack initiation site, the S - N curve $\sigma'_a(N)$ in the HCF regime can be estimated by

$$\sigma'_a = K_{m\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{K_t} \right)^{h_t} K_r^{h_r} \sigma_{a-1} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{a-1} is the S - N curve relationship for as-rolled specimens with polished edges at $R = -1$, $K_{m\sigma}$ is a factor accounting for different load ratios and residual stresses, K_t is the elastic stress concentration factor, and K_r is a reduction factor accounting for surface roughness. The load ratio is defined as the ratio of the minimum applied load (which is proportional to the nominal stress) to the maximum ditto. The exponents h_t and h_r increase the impact of surface roughness and elastic stress concentration as the number of cycles increases, and are given by

$$h_t = \frac{1}{6} \log_{10}(N) \quad (2)$$

and

$$h_r = \frac{1}{2} \log_{10} \left(\frac{N}{10^4} \right), \quad (3)$$

with a minimum value of 0 and a maximum of 1.

According to the FKM-guideline [26,27] the surface roughness reduction factor K_r is given by

$$K_r = 1 - a_R \log_{10}(Rz) \log_{10} \left(\frac{2\sigma_{uts}}{\sigma_{uts,min}} \right), \quad (4)$$

where Rz is the maximum height of the profile given in μm and measured according to standard [28], a_R and $\sigma_{uts,min}$ are material group dependent parameters. In this work the values given for steels in [26], $a_R = 0.22$ and $\sigma_{uts,min} = 400$ MPa, are used.

The expression for $K_{m\sigma}$ is based on the Gerber parabola [24,29], and is given by

$$K_{m\sigma} = 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{mR} + \sigma_{res}}{\sigma_{uts}} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

where σ_{uts} is the uniaxial ultimate tensile strength, σ_{mR} is the nominal mean stress of as-rolled specimens at the load ratio of interest. The stabilized residual stress, after cyclic relaxation, σ_{res} is estimated by

$$\sigma_{res} = \begin{cases} \sigma_y - \sigma_{max}, & \text{if } \sigma_{res}^0 > \sigma_y - \sigma_{max} \\ \sigma_{res}^0, & \text{if } \sigma_{res}^0 \leq \sigma_y - \sigma_{max} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. Cyclic stress relaxation criterion.

where σ_y is the monotonic yield stress and σ_{res}^0 is the surface residual stresses in the loading direction after punching, obtained from the region of crack initiation. For non-reversed loading ($R \neq -1$) the maximum nominal stress for as-rolled specimens at the load ratio of interest, σ_{max} , is given by

$$\sigma_{max} = \sigma_{mR} \left[1 + \left(\frac{1-R}{1+R} \right) \right], \tag{7}$$

where the nominal mean stress σ_{mR} is calculated by

$$\sigma_{mR} = \frac{\sigma_{uts} \sqrt{4 \left(\frac{1+R}{1-R} \right)^2 \sigma_{a-1}^2 + \sigma_{uts}^2 - \sigma_{uts}^2}}{2 \left(\frac{1+R}{1-R} \right) \sigma_{a-1}}, \tag{8}$$

if Gerber parabola mean stress correction applies. For reversed loading σ_{max} equals the stress amplitude. As evident from Eqs. (1)–(8) no calibration parameters are included. The only required information is the uniaxial properties, the surface roughness and the initial residual stresses in the location of crack initiation.

2.4. Cyclic relaxation of compressive residual stresses

The residual stress relaxation model used in [14] originated from the world of welding [30] and was validated for tensile residual stresses. In a much more recent work, also focusing on welding, the cyclic relaxation of compressive residual stresses induced by ultrasonic impact treatment was studied and quantified for three different steels [31]. It was found that the relaxation beyond 100 cycles was negligible, and that the magnitude of the compressive residual stresses decreased monotonically with increased maximum stress. Apart from the maximum stress σ_{max} the monotonic yield strength σ_y was found to influence the relaxation and a quantitative expression was proposed such that

$$\sigma_{res} = \sigma_{res}^0 + 230 \frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_y} \tag{9}$$

Another approach with equal ability, in terms of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), to quantify the relaxation data presented in [31] would be to extend Eq. (6) to

$$\sigma_{res} = \begin{cases} \sigma_y - \sigma_{max}, & \text{if } \sigma_{res}^0 > \sigma_y - \sigma_{max} \\ -0.48\sigma_y + 0.33\sigma_{max}, & \text{if } \sigma_{res}^0 < -0.48\sigma_y + 0.33\sigma_{max} \\ \sigma_{res}^0, & \text{if } -0.48\sigma_y + 0.33\sigma_{max} \leq \sigma_{res}^0 \leq \sigma_y - \sigma_{max}, \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

where the values 0.48 and 0.33 was found by minimizing the RMSE of the prediction versus the values presented in [31]. This way of treating the cyclic compressive stress relaxation would be more consistent with the work presented in [14], which serves as the base for the work presented here. The conditions for the stabilized residual stress presented in Eq. (10) are illustrated in Fig. 2.

3. Material and methods

3.1. Materials

The material used for the study was hot rolled S500MC steel which is a common steel grade for HDV chassis components [1,32]. In [1] the same material, with the same thickness as used in this work, 8 mm, was measured to have the chemical composition presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Chemical composition (wt.%) of S500MC (8 mm) presented in [1].

Mtrl.	Fe	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Al	Nb	V	Ti
S500MC	Bal.	0.052	0.019	1.327	0.009	<0.002	0.036	0.023	0.009	0.046

Fig. 3. Geometry of (a) Punched specimens; (b) Polished HG specimens. Polished edges in red. Rolling direction marked with RD.

Fig. 4. Dog-bone specimen used for tensile testing. The blue arrows explain the terminology used for the micrographs presented in Fig. 5.

3.2. Manufacturing of punched and polished specimens

The punched specimens, presented in Fig. 3(a), were produced using a flat punch mounted in a servo-hydraulic Instron 5585 press. The cutting clearance was 8%. The punch load displacement curve was measured during the punching process and used for material model calibration as described later. The maximum load during punching was around 192 kN, using a blank-holder force of 21 kN. To obtain a set of polished specimens for producing the base material $S-N$ curve, three hourglass (HG) specimens were cut by wire erosion and then polished to $R_a < 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. The longitudinal direction of the specimens was transverse to rolling. The metal sheet surfaces were left in as-rolled condition. The geometry of the hourglass specimens is presented in Fig. 3(b). The hole edge of three punched specimens was ground and polished as an additional comparison in fatigue resistance.

3.3. Tensile testing

Tensile tests were conducted following the ISO 6892 [33] procedure to obtain data for calibration of the plastic flow material model. Three dog-bone specimens, see Fig. 4 were produced by wire erosion in the transverse to rolling direction. The sheet surfaces were left in as-rolled condition.

The mechanical properties from the tensile tests are presented in Table 2 and micrographs representing the different directions are shown in Fig. 5. The microstructure of S500MC of the same thickness and from the same manufacturer was thoroughly studied in [34], where ferrite, pearlite and bainite were found. Hot-rolling, which is used to produce the steel used in this work, involves deformation above the recrystallization temperature, which explains the absence of elongated grains usually found in the rolling direction [35].

Table 2

Yield stress σ_y at 0.2% plastic strain, tensile strength σ_{uts} and elongation of the studied materials. Tested in the transverse to rolling direction.

Specimen	σ_y [MPa]	σ_{uts} [MPa]	Uniform Elong. [%]	Tot. Elong. A80 [%]
1	617.5	658.2	9.5	21.0
2	617.5	657.6	9.6	21.9
3	617.6	658.3	9.2	20.6
Average	618	658	9.4 ± 0.2	21.2 ± 0.7

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. SEM Micrographs in (a) Longitudinal direction; (b) Transverse direction.

Fig. 6. Four-point bending test rig.

3.4. Fatigue testing of polished and punched specimens

In total 56 HCF tests of open-hole and hourglass specimens were conducted in a MTS Bionix servo-hydraulic testing machine following the ISO 1099 [36] procedure in terms of data treatment, test setup, etc. The machine was equipped with a 4-point bending rig, see Fig. 6. The load span of the designed 4-point bending rig was 60 mm, while the support span was 170 mm. The tests were performed in room temperature, 23 ± 2 °C, using sinusoidal wave shapes at a frequency of 15 Hz. Six different load ratios were tested, spanning from $R = -1$ to $R = 0.69$. Apart from the common practice in fatigue of testing reversed ($R = -1$) and pulsating ($R = 0$) loading, the other load ratios were arbitrarily chosen to cover a wide range of possible scenarios. Total fracture was used as failure criteria and specimens reaching $2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles were considered as runouts.

The Basquin relationship was used to fit an S-N curve to the test results of the polished edge specimens according to [37]

$$\sigma_a = CN^{-1/m}, \quad (11)$$

where N is the number of cycles to failure. C and m are calibration parameters.

The Basquin parameters, fitted to experiments of polished specimens, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Basquin parameters for S500MC hourglass specimens with polished edges ($Ra \leq 0.2 \mu\text{m}$) at $R = -1$.

Specimen condition	C [MPa]	m [-]
Hourglass - polished edges	5114	4.608

Table 4

Surface roughness values of the cut edge.

Zone	Rz [μm]	Ra [μm]
Burnish	13.0 ± 5.92	2.14 ± 0.65
Fracture	25.8 ± 12.1	3.86 ± 1.17

Fig. 7. Edge profile of punched S500MC using a cutting clearance 8.0%.**Table 5**

Power law parameters after calibration.

A [MPa]	B [MPa]	n [-]	B_{pn} [MPa]	n_{pn} [-]
600	519	0.6	519	0.4

3.5. Surface roughness and edge profile measurements

To measure the resulting surface roughness induced by the punching process, an optical 3D measurement system, Alicona InfiniteFocusSL and SensoMap Plus software for data treatment, was used. This system enables roughness measurement over a wide region of the cut edge, increasing the probability of finding critical defects that could trigger fatigue failure. The results in terms of the arithmetical mean height Ra and the maximum height of the profile Rz , are summarized in Table 4 according to ISO 21920 [28]. The results show the typical cut edge characteristic of a rougher fracture zone as compared to the burnish zone. To measure the cut edge morphology a punched specimen was cut and mounted in resin before polishing and chemically etching using Nital 2%. The resulting image is presented in Fig. 7.

3.6. Modeling of the shear cutting process to obtain residual stresses

The punching process was simulated using the Finite Element Method (FEM) according to the approach described in [17] where the results were supported by experimental measurements. In [14] the simulated residual stresses from [17] was successfully used for fatigue life estimation, further strengthening the validity of the punching simulations. A mesh size of 0.04 mm was used creating a density of 200 elements over the sheet thickness. Remeshing was used to handle the large deformations. The material model to describe the plastic behavior was calibrated against the tensile test results and the failure model was calibrated to produce a similar punch displacement as measured during the punching experiments.

The uniform plastic flow stress behavior is modeled using an elasto-plastic material model such that

$$\sigma = A + B\varepsilon_p^n, \quad (12)$$

where σ and ε_p are the true stress and strain, respectively. A , B and n are calibration parameters to fit the experimental stress strain data, see Fig. 8(a). In this work the parameters B and n were changed to B_{pn} and n_{pn} , respectively, after a strain of 9.5% to get a good fit after necking. The calibrated parameters are presented in Table 5.

The Rice-Tracey failure model [38] used in this work is described by

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_f = C \exp(1.5\eta) \quad (13)$$

where C is the calibration parameter which was set to $C = 2.2$ to achieve the same punch displacement as in the punching experiment, see Fig. 8(b).

Fig. 8. (a) Engineering tensile test results from experiments and simulations; (b) Measured and simulated punch force–displacement curves (8 mm S500MC).

Fig. 9. Four-point bending FEM simulation and boundary conditions.

3.7. Modeling of four-point bending to obtain the elastic stress concentration

Elastic four-point bending of a specimen of thickness 8 mm was simulated using implicit time integration. A quarter of the nominal specimen geometry was modeled using symmetry conditions. Elements of type 8 point hexahedron was used in the specimen and the rolls. The element size in the region of interest, around the hole, was 0.16–0.17 mm, with increasing size further away to reduce the number of elements. The total number of elements was 508 224. A prescribed vertical (y -direction) motion of 0.3 mm is applied to the center roll. Young’s modulus was set to the same value as in the material model calibration, 200 GPa, Poisson’s ratio to 0.3 and the density to 7830 kg/m³. The nominal stress was calculated using Eq. (14) and the simulated bending moment in the cross section. The simulated maximum stress to compare with the nominal stress for calculation of K_t , was the z -stress in the elements at the outermost edge. The simulation setup and a fringe plot of the stresses are shown in Fig. 9.

The nominal maximum stress σ_{max} used for translating the simulated stress values to elastic stress concentrations was calculated using [39]

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{6M}{t^2(W - D)}, \tag{14}$$

where M was the bending moment measured in the simulation, t and W are the specimen thickness and width, respectively, and D is the diameter of the hole.

4. Reduced fatigue life estimation procedure - Extension to handle out-of-plane bending

Fig. 10. Residual stress field after punching simulation of 8 mm S500MC using cutting clearance 8%. Z direction is normal to the designated crack plane. The limits of the fringe plot are set to $\pm\sigma_{ust}$.

Table 6

Rational function parameters for the residual stress profile [MPa] when L in Eq. (15) is given in millimeters.

Zone	P_4	P_3	P_2	P_1	P_0
Fracture-Burnish	6.652	-100.8	396.9	-42.05	-772.3
Rollover	-14.92	418.5	-3282	8667	-3269
Surf. next to burr	0	192.2	-1346	2798	-2578
Zone	Q_4	Q_3	Q_2	Q_1	Q_0
Fracture-Burnish	0	0	0	0	1
Rollover	1	-8.422	25.35	-29.04	23.2
Surf. next to burr	0	1	-4.805	6.485	2.372

4.1. Extraction of cut edge residual stress profile

The total simulated residual stress field normal to the designated fatigue crack plane is shown in Fig. 10. From this fringe plot a rational function, see Eq. (15), was fitted to the residual stresses in each part of the cut edge, representing the initial residual stress state, i.e. before cyclic relaxation. The parameter values of the approximations are presented in Table 6. The ones and zeroes were predefined in the cases where not all parameters were necessary to obtain a good representation. The elements where the stress was measured and the resulting stress profile along the cut edge are presented in Fig. 11(a) and (b), respectively. The corresponding information for the rollover zone and the surface next to the burr is presented in Fig. 12. The parameter L in Eq. (15) is either profile height or width as defined in Figs. 11 and 12.

$$\sigma_{res}^0 = \frac{P_4 L^4 + P_3 L^3 + P_2 L^2 + P_1 L + P_0}{Q_4 L^4 + Q_3 L^3 + Q_2 L^2 + Q_1 L + Q_0}, \quad (15)$$

4.2. Extraction of elastic stress concentration profile

The simulated variation of the elastic stress concentration going from the hole edge in radial direction is presented in Fig. 13.

This could be approximated by the equation

$$K_t = 10^{-4} \left(\frac{1.0453x^3 - 4.7294x^2 + 8031x + 19834}{x + 1.353} \right), \quad (16)$$

where x is the distance in radial direction from the hole edge given in millimeters.

4.3. Combination of residual stress state, elastic stress concentration and cyclic bending stresses over the cut edge to obtain reduced S-N curve

The following method to estimate the reduced S-N curve in the HCF regime is based on the assumption that the initiation site is dependent on the combined effect of surface roughness, residual stresses, stress relaxation, load amplitude, load ratio, and the

Fig. 11. (a) Layer of cut edge elements, approx. 2-3 elements, used for extraction of the residual stress profile. (b) Simulated residual stress and corresponding approximations.

Fig. 12. (a) Layer of edge elements (2) in the rollover zone and the surface next to the burr used for extraction of the residual stress profile. (b) Simulated residual stress and corresponding approximations.

orientation of the specimen, i.e. which side of the cut edge that is in tension.

The nominal stress amplitude from external loading σ_{aR} experienced by the specimen will vary according to Fig. 14. The red line represents the nominal mean stress σ_{mR} at load ratio R .

Combining Figs. 11–14 means that for every location along the cut edge, the rollover surface and the surface next to the burr, a set of residual stress, applied stress, elastic stress concentration and surface roughness can be obtained. This set can be used with a slightly modified version of the approach summarized in Section 2.3, and presented in detail in [14], to compose a range of $S-N$ curves. It is assumed that failure will occur at the location featuring the lowest curve for a given load and orientation.

The first adjustment of the HCF life estimation procedure consists of the introduction of an initiation site dependent parameter A into Eq. (1)

$$\sigma'_a = \frac{1}{A} K_{m\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{K_t} \right)^{h_t} K_r^{h_r} \sigma_{a-1}, \tag{17}$$

where A is introduced to handle the fact that the nominal applied stress amplitude from bending is defined as the maximum bending stress at the outer surface of the sheet thickness. This stress decreases linearly to zero in the middle of the specimen if elastic conditions are assumed. Hence, if the crack initiate somewhere within the thickness of the sheet, the estimated reduced amplitude must be scaled to yield the nominal maximum applied stress amplitude at the outer surface, which is the stress used for the experimental validation. At thickness $t = 0$ and $t = 8$ the parameter A obtains a value of 1, and $A = 0$ in the center of the

Fig. 13. Variation of the elastic stress concentration K_t .

Fig. 14. Example of nominal stress profile through the thickness of the specimen for load ratio $R = -0.5$. The red dashed line represents the nominal mean stress σ_{mR} and the blue dotted lines represent the nominal stress amplitude profile.

specimen thickness. A is defined by

$$A = \frac{|t - 2L|}{t}, \tag{18}$$

where L is the height of the initiation point along the Y -axis, see Figs. 10 and 11, ranging from 0 at the burr to the sheet thickness.

The second adjustment of the HCF life estimation procedure presented in [14] is to make the mean stress correction factor $K_{m\sigma}$ conditional. It is well known that Gerber mean stress correction is unable to handle negative mean stresses [40]. Due to compressive residual stresses a negative mean stress could occur even if the load ratio imposes a positive mean stress. To handle the effect compressive residual stresses on fatigue, the Goodman based criteria has been used successfully in [41,42]. Hence $K_{m\sigma}$ in this work was defined by

$$K_{m\sigma} = \begin{cases} 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{mR} + \sigma_{res}}{\sigma_{uts}} \right)^2, & \text{if } \sigma_{mR} + \sigma_{res} \geq 0 \\ 1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_{mR} + \sigma_{res}}{\sigma_{uts}} \right), & \text{if } \sigma_{mR} + \sigma_{res} < 0. \end{cases} \tag{19}$$

The third and last adjustment of the HCF life estimation procedure is the addition of a compressive residual stress relaxation criterion according to Eq. (10).

It is important to note that none of the additions would affect the predicting performance presented in [14].

Using the updates presented above, making the procedure more generalized, the $S-N$ curves along the outer edge of the cut edge with surroundings can be computed for a given specimen orientation and load ratio. The resolution in this work was set to 1000 curves along each surface of interest, the cut edge (burnish and fracture zone), the rollover zone and the surface next to the burr.

Fig. 15. Estimated $S-N$ curves for each sub-surface of the cut edge of punched S500MC tested at load ratio (a) $R = -1$; (b) $R = -0.5$. The minimum values for each specimen orientation, i.e. rollover in tension (RT) or burr in tension (BT), are used to create the reduced curves. The orange line represents the base material $S-N$ curve at $R = -1$.

Fig. 16. Estimated $S-N$ curves for each sub-surface of the cut edge of punched S500MC tested at load ratio (a) $R = 0$; (b) $R = 0.25$. The minimum values for each specimen orientation, i.e. rollover in tension (RT) or burr in tension (BT), are used to create the reduced curves. The orange line represents the base material $S-N$ curve at $R = -1$.

To evaluate how the initiation point varied with different stress levels, orientations and load ratios, the initiation site estimation was extracted at four different cycle values ranging from 19 557 ($\sigma_{a-1} = 600$ MPa) to 477 180 ($\sigma_{a-1} = 300$ MPa) cycles, see Table 7. It was assumed that the approach was valid when the maximum nominal applied stress at the outer surface was lower than the yield stress. When this stress exceeds the yield strength the fatigue mechanisms could be assumed to be governed by macroscopic plasticity.

For reversed loading the specimen orientation has no influence on the initiation site since the applied stress is symmetrical, see Fig. 15(a). The results for the other load ratios will be dependent on orientation, see Figs. 15–17.

5. Results

Fig. 17. Estimated S-N curves for each sub-surface of the cut edge of punched S500MC tested at load ratio (a) $R = 0.45$; (b) $R = 0.69$. The minimum values for each specimen orientation, i.e. rollover in tension (RT) or burr in tension (BT), are used to create the reduced curves. The orange line represents the base material S-N curve at $R = -1$.

Table 7

Evaluation points and corresponding estimated initiation sites for different load ratios. The burr is located at height = 0 mm and the intersection between the rollover zone and the burnish zone at height = 7.8 mm. For higher load ratios many the evaluations points are outside the valid range of the approach.

Eval. cycle	Zone in tension	Init. $R = -1$ [mm]	Init. $R = -.5$ [mm]	Init. $R = 0$ [mm]	Init. $R = .25$ [mm]	Init. $R = .45$ [mm]	Init. $R = .69$ [mm]
19 557	Rollover	Roll. 0.4	-	-	-	-	-
44 839	Rollover	Roll. 0.4	-	-	-	-	-
126 500	Rollover	Roll. 1.0	Cut 7.8	-	-	-	-
477 180	Rollover	Roll. 1.4	Roll. 1.1	Roll. 0.7	Roll. 0.6	-	-
19 557	Burr	Roll. 0.4	-	-	-	-	-
44 839	Burr	Roll. 0.4	-	-	-	-	-
126 500	Burr	Roll. 1.0	Cut 0.0	-	-	-	-
477 180	Burr	Roll. 1.4	Cut 0.0	Cut 0.0	Cut 0.0	Cut 0.0	-

5.1. Estimation and validation of fatigue crack initiation site

The estimated initiation sites at the different evaluated number of cycles are presented in Table 7. For validation the estimated initiation sites in four of the tested specimens were compared to the sites found in SEM images, see Fig. 18. The identified crack propagation rate zones are (I) Crack initiation zone (from the damaged region); (II) Stable crack propagation (low crack propagation rate); (III) Unstable crack propagation (high crack propagation rate); (IV) Fracture. The images confirm the expectation that the cracks would initiate at the surface [12], in addition the predicted initiation sites are in reasonably well agreement with the SEM observations.

5.2. Fatigue life: Test and estimation

The out-of-plane HCF test results for polished and punched specimens are presented in Appendix. The estimated reduced S-N curves, predicting performance, and corresponding experiments are presented in Fig. 19. Most of the fatigue tests were conducted with the rollover surface in tension, except for a number of tests at load ratio $R = 0$ marked with BT in the figure.

6. Discussion

6.1. Scatter and prediction accuracy

The prediction accuracy was evaluated using scatter bands with an error factor of 3.0 and 1.5 as seen in Fig. 19(b). Using scatter bands with error factors of this magnitude is a common method to assess fatigue life estimation models [14,43–46]. What performance that can be deemed as sufficient depends on the application but in [14,43,44] it was investigated whether the predictions were within error factor three or not. In [45] predictions within an error factor of 2.5 was deemed as “high performance” and in [47] scatter band of two was considered to indicate a “high degree of predictive accuracy”. In [46] many of the studied models performed outside an error factor of three, while the proposed model predictions were within a factor of around 1.5. The estimations in this work, presented in Fig. 19, fall within a factor of 1.5 in over 70% of the experiments and all are inside a factor of two.

Fig. 18. Stitched SEM images of fatigue fracture surfaces. Identified initiation sites marked with white circles and predicted locations marked with yellow lines representing areas with maximum 10% difference in predicted reduced nominal stress amplitude as compared to the reduced $S-N$ curve. Arrows are added as additional indications of the estimated initiation sites. (a) Specimen SP5 tested at $R = -1$. Number of cycles to failure: 78 517; (b) SP13 tested at $R = -1$. Number of cycles to failure: 73 587; (c) SP7 tested at $R = -1$. Number of cycles to failure: 681 728; (d) Specimen SP9 tested at $R = 0$, evaluated at $N = 131 862$. Number of cycles to failure in experiment: 119 331.

6.2. Reduction as compared to specimens with polished holes

Fatigue specimens with polished holes were tested at reversed loading to further examine whether the punching process has any influence on bending fatigue or if the reduction in nominal stress amplitude can be traced to the elastic stress concentration factor and the load ratio only. The results, as compared to testing of hourglass and punched specimens are presented in Fig. 20.

The largest tensile residual stresses in cut edges from punching does not coincide with the maximum elastic stress concentration, nor with the maximum applied stress from out of plane bending. Instead, FEM simulations of the punching process indicate that these regions feature beneficial compressive residual stresses, which partly might explain the unexpectedly small fatigue life reduction as compared to specimens with polished hole edges. The fact that a reduction can be observed at all seems to be due to the tensile residual stresses appearing in the rollover zone some distance away from the hole in radial direction.

6.3. Sensitivity analysis - Residual stress profile variation

The residual stress profiles are obtained from simulations and hence provide a source of uncertainty. However, the simulation method to obtain the stress profile is validated [17] and the residual stress results from such a simulation was used in [14] to

Fig. 19. (a) Estimated reduced S-N curves; (b) Prediction performance.

Fig. 20. Reversed ($R = -1$) fatigue test results of different specimen types.

estimate uniaxial fatigue life. Qualitatively, the stress profile obtained in this work agrees well with the experimentally measured residual stresses in [12] for a similar material grade and cutting clearance. It should also be stressed that the values obtained both experimentally and in simulations are dependent on the resolution or measurement volume due to the high stress gradients. Hence, the main uncertainty in terms of residual stress profile comes from the magnitude of the stresses. To assess the sensitivity of different initial residual stress magnitudes the stresses were changed $\pm 50\%$. It was found that the predicting performance was still within an error factor of three.

6.4. High load ratios and non-propagating cracks

The results presented in Fig. 19 imply that the results for load ratios up to $R = 0$ is accurately estimated, while for higher load ratios an increasing under-prediction of the fatigue life is seen. One explanation for this can be found using FEM simulations considering plasticity. Three experiments were conducted at $R = 0.25$ using a nominal stress value of around 230 MPa, creating a nominal maximum stress of 613 MPa. Four point bending of the tested geometry can be simulated using this stress level to obtain an updated “initial” residual stress profile. The original residual stresses from punching is considered in the simulation by mapping the total residual stress field to a three dimensional mesh as shown in Fig. 21.

The experiments at $R = 0.25$, and the simulation discussed in this section, were performed with the rollover zone in tension. The original residual stress from punching, mapped to three dimensional elements, and the resulting profiles after applying a maximum nominal stress of around 613 MPa, are presented in Fig. 22(a) and (b). In this case it is assumed that fatigue will not take place at the surface next to the burr and hence the residual stress profile in that surface is not presented. In the process of mapping stresses

Fig. 21. Residual stresses in the z-direction of a punched specimen. Fringe plot limits are set to $\pm\sigma_{us}$.

Fig. 22. Residual stresses in z-direction along (a) cut edge (burnish and fracture zone) and (b) rollover surface. The blue dashed lines are curves fitted to the simulated residual stresses in z-direction from the punching process. The red lines represent the residual stress from punching after mapping to a coarser 3D hexagonal mesh. The orange lines represent the residual stresses after subsequent four point bending at the nominal stress level experienced by the $R = 0.25$ experiments.

from 2D axisymmetric elements to 3D hexagonal elements the local geometry of the cut edge is slightly altered, the mesh size is increased to reduce simulation time, and axisymmetry no longer applies due to the elongated shape of the specimens. This causes the stresses to find a new equilibrium state which causes a slight difference in residual stresses, see Fig. 22(a) and (b).

It is evident that at the load level used for specimens tested at load ratio $R = 0.25$, the detrimental tensile residual stresses in the rollover zone decreases. If the new residual stress profiles are used, the reduced $S-N$ curve shown in Fig. 23 is obtained for $R = 0.25$ following the fatigue life estimation procedure suggested in this work. The $S-N$ curve for $R = 0$ created using the original stress profile is added for comparison, showing that the results for $R = 0.25$ seems to overlap the $R = 0$ results, which is supported by the experiments. This suggests that for high load ratios it is necessary incorporate the effects of plasticity even for fatigue at relatively high number of cycles, making estimations at these load ratios cumbersome. Not considering these effects results in a conservative estimation of the $S-N$ curve.

Fig. 23. Estimation of reduced $S-N$ curves using the updated residual stress profiles for $R = 0.25$ and the original profile for $R = 0$.

Another phenomena that could affect the results are non-propagating cracks [48,49]. Considering this, the estimated reduced $S-N$ curves could be interpreted as the curves that would be obtained experimentally if all cracks that initiate would propagate to failure. Following the reasoning in [48,49] the base material fatigue limit at reversed loading is the point where no cracks initiate, and reduced curves, considering for example elastic stress concentration, should reach this state at the same number of cycles. However, Frost [48,49] found that for sufficiently high stress concentration factors cracks could initiate but due to the drastically reduced stress field ahead of the crack tip they did not propagate. All test results for high load ratios ($R > 0$) in this work was made with the rollover zone in tension where the initial residual stresses are relatively small and does not seem to introduce large stress gradients. Instead, this gradient could come from the combined effect of the elastic stress concentration factor and the applied bending stress. For a given stress amplitude the applied stress gradient increases with increased load ratio, as evident in Fig. 14. Hence it could be assumed that the curves should reach a plateau, either if the local stress is below the base material fatigue limit so that no cracks initiate, or the stress gradients become so high that the applied global stresses are small in comparison the local maximum stress, i.e. cracks will initiate but not propagate. This is not reflected using the approach presented here.

6.5. Effect of specimen orientation

Looking at Figs. 15–17 it is evident that for all load ratios the lowest $S-N$ curve for specimens with the rollover zone in tension does not differ significantly to the burr in tension ditto. Hence, it is suggested that the effect of specimen orientation, and by extension, the effect of punching direction in real components is small in out-of-plane bending fatigue. This is also implied by the $R = 0$ fatigue test results.

6.6. Base material $S-N$ curve sensitivity

The fatigue tests of hourglass specimens with polished edge were scarce and hence the base material $S-N$ curve σ_{a-1} presents a source of uncertainty to the results. To evaluate the impact of this the slope ($1/m$), see Eq. (11), of σ_{a-1} was modified $\pm 40\%$. Then the parameter C in the same equation was set so that the curves intersect with the experiment at the highest stress level, see Fig. 24(a). This point was selected because the scatter in test results is expected to decrease as the stress increase. In addition $S-N$ curves at an error factor of 1.5 from σ_{a-1} were evaluated. The predicting performance for different curves are presented in Fig. 24(b). For the evaluated curves the predicting performance stayed within an error factor of three, while some points are close to the limit on the conservative side.

6.7. Extension to other materials and negative load ratios

The compressive stress relaxation model implemented in this work was extracted from testing of steels with relatively similar mechanical properties as the steel used in this work. It is unclear if the model would work for steels with different plastic hardening behavior. In such cases the fixed parameters (-0.48 and 0.33) would most likely change.

The approach was validated for load ratios between -1 and 0.69 . The validity of extending the approach to loading purely on the compression side is uncertain.

Fig. 24. (a) Base material S-N curves used for sensitivity analysis; (b) Corresponding predicting performance.

Fig. 25. Estimation of the effect of improved “Shot-Blasted” (SB) outer surfaces so that fatigue failure only occur in the thickness range $0.5 \text{ mm} \leq t \leq 7.5 \text{ mm}$.

6.8. Effect of improving the outer surfaces

Shot-blasting is often used on HDV components featuring punched holes. This improves fatigue properties of the surfaces, but for thick sheets and for holes with small diameter the amount of improvement close to the center of the specimens is uncertain due to the geometric difficulty in reaching these regions with the blasting media. In Fig. 25 an improvement of the outer surfaces is assumed, so that fatigue cracks only initiate in the central parts ($0.5 \text{ mm} \leq t \leq 7.5 \text{ mm}$) of the cut edge. The estimated increase of the S-N curves at $N = 5 \cdot 10^5$ are around 14% for $R = 0$ and 18% for $R = -1$.

6.9. Durability of chassis components

The fatigue assessment in this work was made on specimens including punched holes to increase the understanding of the interaction between bending loads, residual stresses, surface roughness and stress concentration. The as-rolled surfaces were left without polishing as the method presented in [14] was validated in that manner. On component level chassis components are often subject to additional manufacturing processes such as for example welding and shot peening or sandblasting. These processes and their sequence can affect the residual stresses, surface roughness and microstructure [20]. In addition a varying load spectra could be expected. Hence, the results in this work should be extrapolated to component level only with careful consideration of these processes. Fatigue testing on component level is necessary to evaluate the durability. To reduce cost and time in product development accelerated test methods, reproducing service conditions and failure modes, should be considered [50]. These methods also account for scatter in the manufacturing process which will affect the fatigue life.

7. Conclusions

The approach for estimation of reduced fatigue life due to punching presented in [14] is extended from uniaxial to out-of-plane bending fatigue by estimation of the reduced $S-N$ curves in all possible initiation sites, assuming surface initiated fatigue. By combining the lowest $S-N$ curves at every cycle the total $S-N$ curve is composed. A cyclic relaxation criterion for compressive residual stresses is implemented and the positive effect on fatigue life due to compressive mean stresses is considered using Goodman correction in the negative mean stress range. The effect of specimen orientation and load ratio is estimated and validated experimentally, and the possible improvement of surface treatments is estimated. The robustness of the approach is evaluated by varying the initial residual stress profiles and the $S-N$ curve for the base material.

The main conclusions from this study are:

1. Despite the high tensile residual stresses in the middle of the cut edge, the fatigue cracks tend to initiate at, or close to the outer surfaces, i.e. the rollover zone and the surface next to the burr due to the locally high applied stress amplitude.
2. FEM simulations indicate that the residual stresses from punching in these regions are compressive where the elastic stress concentration reaches its maximum, while tensile residual stresses appear at a lower elastic stress concentration. This could provide an explanation to the unexpectedly small difference in fatigue life between specimens with punched and polished holes.
3. The specimen orientation, i.e. which side of the cut edge that is under tension, has a minor influence on fatigue life. Hence, the importance of punching direction is assumed to be negligible for components subject to out-of-plane bending. It is important to note that no significant burr formation was found on the specimens.
4. Fatigue life improving post processes, such as shot-blasting, could be beneficial even if the central parts of the cut edge remains unaffected of the post-process.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

David Gustafsson: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sergi Parareda:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Henrik Sieurin:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Erik Olsson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. Fatigue test results

See [Table A.8](#).

Table A.8

S500MC out-of-plane fatigue test results of polished hourglass (HG), polished with hole (H/POL) and punched (P) specimens cut in transverse to rolling direction. Number of cycles rounded to the nearest ten. The specimens with the burr zone oriented in tension are marked with *BT*. The specimens used for crack initiation site measurements are marked with specimen identification number (SP). The stress amplitudes are given as nominal maximum amplitude from the applied bending without stress concentration factors. The specimens SP5, SP7, SP13 and SP9 are used for evaluation of the crack initiation sites.

Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]	Edge cond.	Load ratio	σ_a [MPa]	N [cycles]
HG	-1	473	60 988	P <i>BT</i>	0	355	36 380
HG	-1	425	92 931	P <i>BT</i>	0	355	29 506
HG	-1	328	324 070	P	0	350	52 722
H/POL	-1	473	39 715	P <i>BT</i>	0	327	40 689
H/POL	-1	376	81 423	P <i>BT</i>	0	309	46 764
H/POL	-1	328	178 942	P <i>BT</i>	0	306	74 508
P	-1	519	21 075	P <i>BT</i>	0	305	74 253
P	-1	473	30 736	P <i>BT</i>	0	283	80 819
P	-1	473	32 929	P <i>BT</i>	0	281	78 150
P	-1	466	34 635	P <i>BT</i>	0	261	129 723
P	-1	422	56 805	P <i>BT</i> SP9	0	260	119 331
P SP13	-1	380	73 587	P	0	258	151 589
P SP5	-1	378	78 517	P <i>BT</i>	0	257	109 827
P	-1	376	83 913	P <i>BT</i>	0	234	220 873
P	-1	355	103 939	P <i>BT</i>	0	233	118 154
P	-1	353	103 547	P <i>BT</i>	0	214	295 521
P	-1	352	95 079	P <i>BT</i>	0	211	306 019
P	-1	328	133 975	P <i>BT</i>	0	210	286 655
P	-1	283	234 122	P <i>BT</i>	0	188	644 745
P	-1	283	292 807	P	0	187	406 665
P	-1	280	255 574	P <i>BT</i>	0	185	504 981
P	-1	257	440 713	P <i>BT</i>	0	166	RO
P	-1	237	517 261	P	0.25	230	236 268
P	-1	237	643 630	P	0.25	230	630 629
P SP7	-1	235	681 728	P	0.25	230	424 003
P	-1	189	RO	P	0.45	165	RO
P	-0.5	253	234 477	P	0.45	145	RO
P <i>BT</i>	0	357	36 138	P	0.69	51	RO

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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